

Satellite information downscaled to urban air quality in Bulgaria – results from the SIDUAQ project

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Abstract: The ESA funded project SIDUAQ made it possible, for the first time in Bulgaria, to use satellite data on atmospheric chemistry for improvement of air pollution modelling at national and local scale, and to use TROPOMI-S5p data for elaboration of maps for particulate matter (PM) concentrations at ground-level. We discuss the effect of satellite data assimilation in the Bulgarian Chemical Weather Forecasting System (BgCWFS) on different pollutants concentrations based on simulations for one summer and one winter months. We present results from downscaling of BgCWFS results for the territory of Bulgaria (9 km spatial resolution) down to city of Plovdiv (250 m resolution) by means of the Local Air Quality Modelling System (LAQMS). The performance of the models is evaluated based on comparison to observational data and to models from the Copernicus CAMS service. The results of models for converting TROPOMI –S5p aerosol data to PM concentrations over Bulgaria are also outlined.

Използване на сателитна информация за качеството на атмосферния въздух в градска среда в България – резултати от проекта SIDUAQ

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Резюме: Проектът SIDUAQ, финансиран от ЕКА, даде възможност за първи път в България сателитни данни за атмосферна химия да се използват за подобряване на моделни системи за качество на атмосферния въздух (КАВ) в национален и локален мащаб, както и за създаване на карти за разпределението на фините прахови частици (ФПЧ) в България по аерозолни данни от TROPOMI –S5p. Дискутира се ефекта от усвояване на сателитни данни в Българската система за прогноза на химическото време (BgCWFS) върху приземните концентрации на различни замърсители на база пресмятания за един зимен и един летен месец. Представени са резултати от свеждане на изходните данни от BgCWFS (хоризонтална резолюция 9 км) към локално ниво за района на град Пловдив (250 м резолюция) посредством дисперсионната локална система LAQMS. Моделните резултати са оценени на база сравнения с наблюдения и сравнения с резултати от модели на системата Коперник – CAMS. Показани са и резултати от модели за конвертиране на аерозолни данни от TROPOMI –S5p към приземни концентрации на ФПЧ в България.

Introduction

Air quality issues in urban areas in Bulgaria continue to be of big concern, as EU limit values for particulate matter concentrations are often exceeded, despite the measures for reduction the emissions of pollutants. Better understanding of air pollution problems is the key for effective measures. Recognizing that air pollution is a complex problem linked to various processes over different spatial and temporal scales, requiring multi-disciplinary approach with application of different tools, the project SIDUAQ was carried out by a team composed of two partners with complementary expertise. The National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) has a long-year experience in development and applications of numerical air quality modelling systems at national and urban scale. The Space Research and Technology Institute at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (SRTI-BAS) is the leading institution in Bulgaria in the field of remote sensing of the Earth and regional and global monitoring of the environment and security.

Within SIDUAQ [1, <http://space.bas.bg/SIDUAQ/>] we investigated the possibility of using satellite retrieved data on atmospheric chemistry for improving the capabilities of air quality modelling systems for surface concentrations of key pollutants at national and local level, for analysing air pollution problems in Bulgaria, and for exploring the spatial distribution of pollutants at ground-level based on data from TROPOMI-S5p. The results from the analysis of regional and local pollution over Bulgaria based on multi-year GOME2 and recent TROPOMI-S5p data were presented and discussed in [2,3].

Here we focus on the results related to air quality modelling with satellite data assimilation and on results related to converting TROPOMI-S5p aerosol data to surface particulate matter concentrations over Bulgaria.

Results from air quality modelling with the upgraded system BgCWFS

The operational chemical weather forecast system BgCWFS [4, 5] based on the meteorological model WRF [6] and the chemical transport model CMAQ [7], was set-up to assimilate GOME-2 (MetOP A,B,C) data for aerosol optical depth (AOD) and the columnar NO₂ (VCD_NO₂) and SO₂ (VCD_SO₂) over 3 nested domains – Europe with horizontal resolution 81 km, Balkan Peninsula (27 km) and domain Bulgaria (9 km). Data at the time of satellite overpass hour (set to 09:00 UTC) were used. BgCWFS is running operationally at NIMH since 2012. The system provides 72h forecast for key pollutants – ozone, nitrogen dioxide and particulate matter over the 3 mentioned domains, plus another two domains – Sofia region (3 km) and Sofia city (1 km).

For SIDUAQ the system was modified for: a) calculation of AOD and vertical column densities of NO₂ and SO₂; b) assimilation of GOME-2 data; c) interface for links to local air quality management system for Plovdiv (LAQMS); d) post-processing of output to facilitate model validation. Five different schemes were investigated for estimation of aerosol extinction coefficients and AOD [8], with the algorithm FlexAOD [9] selected for further use. The assimilation of satellite retrieved data is made for the three nested domains (Europe- Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria) and to our knowledge, represents a novelty, as in the literature satellite data algorithms applied for one domain can be found. Another novelty is the simultaneous assimilation of AOD, VCD_NO₂ and VCD_SO₂.

To investigate the effects of satellite data assimilation, BgCWFS was run in two versions: *mod* (without satellite data assimilation), and *sat* (with assimilation of satellite data). Simulations for two periods of one month – August 2017 and February 2019 were carried out in off-line mode of BgCWFS, with output on hourly basis for each version of the system.

The performance of BgCWFS in the two versions was studied using different approaches: a) analysis of (*sat-mod*) differences on hourly and monthly basis for different model domains; b) comparison to observed concentrations at regular air quality (AQ) stations in Bulgaria; c) comparison to AOD at AERONET stations; d) comparison to results of third party advanced modelling systems, or model inter-comparison. These models include the EMEP-MS-CW [10] used regularly by the European Environmental Agency for annual assessment of the air quality and transboundary pollution in Europe, the operational Copernicus regional air quality system CAMS-ENS [11], and the global operational Copernicus model providing also atmospheric chemistry data CAMS-ECMWF [12]. We will discuss below part of these extensive analysis.

Differences (*sat-mod*). The spatial distribution of pollutants was analyzed for the difference between the BgCWFS outputs with assimilation of satellite data (*sat*) and without satellite data assimilation (*mod*). A common behavior was found for the pollutants PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃ in the three model domains. At the time of satellite overpass hour (Hs fixed to 09:00 UTC) a disturbance in the fields appears resampling area source of pollution. These disturbances have different shapes that evolve in time due to atmospheric transport and transformations. The values of the differences decrease with time and became small or disappear by the end of the day (for ozone they remain to the next day).

More details can be found in [13]. Fig.1 shows, as example, the difference (AODsat-AODmod) in domain Balkan Peninsula at different time intervals on a selected day. More maps can be found at the dedicated web page <http://meteorology.meteo.bg/siduaq/about.html>.

Fig. 1. Time evolution of the AOD difference (*sat-mod*) on 22.08.2017 at h=0, 8, 9(Hs), 10, 14, 23, in model domain Balkan Peninsula

The domain mean values of the differences (*sat-mod*) of surface and columnar parameters are shown in Fig.2 for domain Balkan Peninsula. The values are monthly means for the summer and the winter months. The assimilation of satellite data lead to an increase in all domain mean parameters, except for NO₂ and respectively VCD_NO₂. The increase in the summer month is in general higher than the increase in the winter month. One of the reason is in the higher availability of satellite data in summer. For SO₂ (VCD_SO₂) the effect in the winter month is more pronounced, and is probably linked to higher share of emission sources from energy production.

Fig. 2. Monthly differences (*sat-mod*) in domain mean parameters for domain Balkan Peninsula, left – surface parameters (units are μgm⁻³), right – columnar parameters (units for VCD are μgm⁻²)

Comparison to surface observations. Data from about 34 AQ stations in Bulgaria were used to test the performance of the two versions of BgCWFS obtained for domain Bulgaria. Stations with more than 75% data availability were included, for PM_{2.5} the stations with sufficient data were 8 for the summer month and only 4 for the winter month. The comparison of the monthly mean values (Fig.3) indicates clear improvement of *sat* model results for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and SO₂. The normalised mean bias for PM₁₀ is reduced by the *sat* results by more than 30%.The notable underestimation of NO₂, suggested also by the domain mean values, points to deficits in the emissions data in BgCWFS.

Fig. 3. Mean monthly concentrations (μgm^{-3}) of OBS, and *mod* and *sat* of BgCWFS results for August 2017 (left) and February 2019 (right)

Comparison to CAMS-ECMWF This model inter-comparison was useful in analyzing the spatial distribution of vertical column densities, as these parameters are not measured. Domain mean columnar parameters differ by BgCWFS and CAMS-ECMWF, notably for columnar SO₂, Fig.4. Possible reason is linked to different emissions input. We recall, however, that at surface level the modelled values by BgCWFS with satellite data assimilation (*sat*) are more closed to observational ones. The lower domain mean values for VCD_NO₂ indicate again that the emission sources related to nitrogen oxides, used in BgCWFS, need to be revised.

Fig. 4. Monthly mean values of columnar parameters averaged in domain Bulgaria, left – for August 2017; right - for February 2019

More results from the model inter-comparison for particulate matter can be found in [14].

Results from air quality modelling with the upgraded system LAQMS for Plovdiv

The Local Air Quality Management System of the city of Plovdiv (LAQMS), was developed at NIMH and is being working operationally since 2004 [15]. The system has 4 main modules: meteorological pre-processor, emission modules, dispersion modules, and interface for appropriate presentation of modelling results (Expert Module). All these modules were upgraded within the project SIDUAQ for including satellite retrieved data on air pollution down to urban scale, but also for incorporating more precise data for local scale emission sources on fine scale air pollution simulations. The simulations are performed by a combination of emission module for specific group of sources (household heating, traffic, industrial, and all) and two dispersion models complementary to each other – Poltran (an Eulerian type) and AUSTAL2000 (a Lagrangian type, [16]). A characteristic feature of LAQMS is the possibility to calculate the concentrations caused by different emission sources in the city, and from outside. In this way it allows to assess the impact of the different groups of emission sources on the air quality and to take the most appropriate action for air quality improvement.

LAQMS was set-up for 2 domains: domain “Plovdiv region” (horizontal resolution 1kmx1km) and domain “Plovdiv city” (horizontal resolution 250x250m), Fig.5. The systems was linked with the output of BgCWFS. The output of BgCWFS for the two domains consisted in 24 meteorological parameters at surface level and 8 pollutants. For some meteorological parameters 3D data using the 11 lowest vertical levels of BgCWFS were extracted. Using the meteorological pre-processor of LAQMS the hourly data from BgCWFS were reformatted and interpolated to the computational grids of LAQMS. The value of the parameter at a point of the computational grid is obtained as a linear interpolation from the four points of the BgCWFS grid between which the point of the computational grid falls.

Fig. 5. The computational grids for Plovdiv: domain “region” (left) and domain “city” (right)
 black dots: BgCWFS’s grids points for wind components data, red dots: BgCWFS’s grids points for other meteorological & pollutants variables, shaded areas – settlements

Upgrade of the emissions in LAQMS. The emission module of LAQMS was significantly modified applying a “bottom-up” approach for emissions inventory in ArcGIS environment. This approach is a novelty in urban air pollution modelling in Bulgaria. The emissions from the traffic and the household heating were compiled based on data from traffic camera and answers in 450 questionnaires on type of heating distributed in the city of Plovdiv. Fig.6 shows as example the emissions of PM10 from household heating and road traffic.

Fig. 6. Emission of PM10 (kg/h) left: from the residential heating, right: from the segments of the road network in the city of Plovdiv

Comparison to surface observations in Plovdiv. The LAQMS model results were compared to data from the two automatic monitoring stations in the city – Kamenitza station (urban background type) and Trakia station (traffic station). Fig.7 and Fig.8 show observed and modelled monthly mean PM10 concentrations for the two months, respectively for each station.

Fig. 7. PM10 concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\text{m}^{-3}$) at Kamenitza station; left – mean for February 2019; right – mean for August 2017; OBS- observed PM10, the modelled values LAQMS+BgCWFS are without (No sat data) and with satellite data assimilation (With sat data); The colors indicate the contribution of different sources to the total modelled PM10

Fig. 8. PM10 concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at Trakia station; details as in Fig. 7

The LAQMS results provide the PM10 concentrations due to various emission sources – household heating, traffic, industry, and the background concentrations, provided by BgCWFS. As seen in Figs. 7, 8 the contribution of the household heating to PM10 concentrations is significant in the winter month at both stations, on average it is about 45%. The contribution of the traffic is more evident at Trakia station, especially in the summer month, when it contributes with 78% to the monthly mean PM10 concentrations. The effect of the satellite data assimilation is seen in the contribution of the “background” provided by BgCWFS. This contribution is on average 36% for the summer month, and 25% for the winter month.

In the “satellite” case, the background concentrations are by 50% higher for February 2019 and by 95% higher for August 2017 with respect to “no satellite” case. The relatively big difference in the contribution of the background concentrations in “no satellite” and “satellite” cases indicates the important of the satellite data inclusion in the systems BgCWFS and LAQMS. In fact, the relative error between model and observation, averaged for the two stations and two months, was reduced from modulus value 16% in case without satellite data assimilation to modulus value 9.6% in case with satellite data assimilation.

More results from the simulations with LAQMS can be found on a dedicated web page, <http://meteorology.meteo.bg/siduaq/about.html>.

Upgrade of the Expert Module of LAQMS. The output of the LAQMS system is on hourly basis – hourly maps of pollutant concentrations. On the other hand, most of the air quality standards are defined on daily, monthly, seasonal or yearly basis. The “row” hourly information is not very convenient to use by the air quality decision makers. The task of the Expert module of LAQMS is to post-process the hourly concentrations into values more meaningful for local AQ experts. A notable feature of the LAQMS and its Expert module is their possibility to simulate separately the dispersion of pollutants, emitted by different group emission sources - household heating, traffic, industry. Fig.9 shows, as example, screenshots of the Expert module for mean monthly PM10 concentrations in the city in February 2019 caused by the residential heating, and by the traffic in the city.

Fig. 9. Mean monthly PM10 surface concentration for Feb 2019; left: from residential heating, right: from the traffic

Inferring PM10, PM2.5 at ground level from TROPOMI-S5p

Collection and processing of TROPOMI-S5p data and data observed at the ground. Fig.10 shows the algorithm for collecting TROPOMI-S5p level 2 AAI data in two different wavelengths – 340–388 nm and 380–354 for the territory of Bulgaria (BG).

Fig. 10. Algorithm for collecting AAI data from TROPOMI S5p for the territory of BG

DB-S-5P-Pre Ops Product Type-L2_AER_AI –this is the Source Product Type-L2_AER_AI file, available from [17]

FID-BG – controls if L2_AER_AI – files are available for the territory of BG

SDB-AAI-BG Product Type-L2_AER_AI is the created Data Base with L2_AER_AI – files for the territory of BG.

A database was created with all files containing AAI data over Bulgaria for the period from July 2018 to December 2019. The next step in the processing of these data is the conversion from AAI to AOD. The algorithm, shown in Fig.11, is based on empirical relationship [18]. A toolbox model was elaborated in ArcGIS environment for the automatized conversion of the database files from AAI to AOD for the territory of Bulgaria (**SDB-AAI-BG** to **SDB-AOD-BG**).

Fig. 11. Algorithm for conversion of AAI to AOD for files for the territory of BG (SDB-AAI-BG to SDB-AOD-BG, DD – Decimal Degree, SDB-AAI-BG – Sub Data Base of AAI for territory of Bulgaria, SDB-AOD-BG - Sub Data Base of AOD for territory of Bulgaria

The data for PM10 and PM2.5 observed at automatic monitoring stations (AMS), maintained by the national Executive Environmental Agency, were downloaded from [19] and processed for extract data at the time of the satellite overpass (the hour closest to the satellite overpass time is used).

Models for converting AOD to PM10 and PM2.5 at ground-level. Different models for AOD to PM10 and PM2.5 conversion were created in a toolbox in ArcGIS, see Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Block diagram of different models for AOD to PM10 and PM2.5 conversion

The abbreviations refer to:

SDB-AMS-BG PM_{2.5} – SubDataBase with measurements of PM_{2.5} by AMS in BG

SDB-AMS-BG PM₁₀ – SubData Base with measurements of PM₁₀ by AMS in BG

RA PM_{2.5} – Regression Analysis between AOD and PM_{2.5} using SDB-AMS-BG PM_{2.5} and SDB-AOD-BG

RA PM₁₀ – Regression Analysis between AOD and PM₁₀ using SDB-AMS-BG PM₁₀ and SDB-AOD-BG

RE PM_{2.5} – Regression Equation after AOD and PM_{2.5} using SDB-AMS-BG PM_{2.5} and SDB-AOD-BG

RE PM₁₀ – Regression Equation after AOD and PM₁₀ using SDB-AMS-BG PM₁₀ and SDB-AOD-BG

EFC PM_{2.5} – Equation Function Calculation using minimizing of Discrete Function Measurement (DFM) from SDB-AMS-BG PM_{2.5} and Polynomial Function(PF)

EFC PM₁₀ – Equation Function Calculation using minimizing of Discrete Function Measurement (DFM) from SDB-AMS-BG PM₁₀ and Polynomial Function (PF)

CCF PM_{2.5} – Comparison Calculation Function and Regression Equation. Testing of the models and choice for the final model.

CCF PM₁₀ – Comparison Calculation Function and Regression Equation. Testing of the models and choice for the final model.

FMC AOD to PM_{2.5} – Final Model Calculation AOD to PM_{2.5}

FMC AOD to PM₁₀ – Final Model Calculation AOD to PM₁₀.

The criteria for selection of **FMC AOD to PM₁₀ / to PM_{2.5}** / is maximal correlation between the values of the Discrete Function Measurement (DFM) and the respective Model Calculation AOD to PM₁₀ / PM_{2.5}.

$$(1) \quad DFM_{2.5} = \{PM_{2.5}(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m)\}$$

$$(2) \quad DFM_{10} = \{PM_{10}(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m)\}$$

$$(3) \quad PF_{2.5} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * AOD(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m) + \dots + \alpha_k * AOD^k(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m)$$

$$(4) \quad PF_{10} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * AOD(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m) + \dots + \beta_k * AOD^k(t_i, \omega_m, \varphi_m)$$

The values of the coefficients $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k$ and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_k$ in the expressions (3) and (4) for $PF_{2.5}$ and PF_{10} are obtained from the calculation of the two systems of linear equations with respectively k unknown $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k$ and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_k$. The two systems of linear equations are obtained after the minimization of the Difference Functions $\Delta_{2.5}(\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k)$ and $\Delta_{10}(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_k)$.

$$(5) \quad MIN \{ \Delta_{2.5}(\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k) \} = \sum_{i=1}^N \{ DFM_{2.5} - PF_{2.5} \}$$

$$(6) \quad MIN \{ \Delta_{10}(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_k) \} = \sum_{i=1}^N \{ DFM_{10} - PF_{10} \}$$

where:

- ω_m, φ_m are the coordinates of AMS (longitude, latitude in Decimal Degree (DD));
- $\alpha_0 = 25.5696, \alpha_1 = -158.886, \alpha_2 = 323.464$;
- $\beta_0 = 67.89, \beta_1 = -289.86, \beta_2 = 488.08$;
- t_i is the UTC end of time interval for scanning the territory of Bulgaria from S-5P TROPOMI

Upon substitution with the values for the coefficients, the following empiric equations are formed for the AOD to PM2.5 and AOD to PM10 conversion:

$$(7) \quad PM_{2.5}(t_i) = 25.5696 - 158.886 * AOD(t_i) + 323.464 * AOD^2(t_i)$$

$$(8) \quad PM_{10}(t_i) = 67.89 - 289.86 * AOD(t_i) + 488.08 * AOD^2(t_i)$$

Fig. 13 shows the **FMC for AOD to PM2.5 and PM10**.

Fig. 13. Conversion model of AOD to PM2.5 and to PM10

The models for AOD to PM10 and PM2.5 calculation were embedded in the ArcGIS toolbox. The comparison between AOD retrieved PM values and observed PM concentrations at AMS was carried out using two of the developed models:

- Empirical polynomial discrete function of 2-nd order (PF); and
- Statistical one (non-linear regression of 2-nd order (STF).

Bi-linear interpolation in space is used for matching to TROPOMI –S5p points and AMS locations. Further, satellite data retrieved by S5P-TROPOMI were not used in case the presence of cloud cover for the territory of Bulgaria was greater than 10%.

Based on the collected data during the period 2018-2020, the correlation coefficient and the errors between the values of PM10 and PM2.5 measured by AMS and those obtained from different models after AOD conversion of data by S5P-TROPOMI were calculated. The correlation coefficient of the sample data for PM2.5 is $R = 0.873 - 0.875$, and for PM10 is $R = 0.863 - 0.866$. The error for PM2.5 is $\pm 8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, for PM10 it is $\pm 10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ with insignificant changes for the two conversion models PF and STF.

Maps for PM10 and PM2.5. Using the developed techniques and models various maps for the spatial distribution of PM10 and PM2.5 in Bulgaria were produced. Fig.14 and Fig.15 show, as example the maps for one summer and one winter day.

Fig. 14. PM2.5 (left) and PM10 (right) concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) on 06.08.2018, overpass time 09:50:51-11:32:21 UTC, b1-band: 380 to 340 nm. Note different scales

Fig. 15. PM2.5 (left) and PM10 (right) concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) on 07.12.2019, overpass time 11:36:10-11:41:10 UTC, b2-band: 388 to 354 nm. Note different scales

A very important advantage of the applied techniques is the fact that PM surface concentrations can be obtained over the whole territory of the country with the resolution of TROPOMI data (7 km x 3.5 km). Thus, they could be used to complement standard AQ monitoring data and indicate possible AQ problems where standard measurements are missing. However, the satellite retrieved PM concentrations refer only to the time of the satellite overpass, and data availability in case of clouds can be limited. Thus, long-term data sets are required to provide a basis for reliable AQ assessment using satellite retrieved aerosol data.

Conclusions

SIDUAQ activities addressed, for the first time in Bulgaria, the use of satellite retrieved data on atmospheric chemistry for improvement of air pollution modelling and air quality management at urban scale, for assessment of the spatial distribution of surface particulate matter concentrations, and for analysis of multi-year variability of key pollutants in the country and selected hot-spot areas.

This was achieved by using a combination of various models (meteorological model, chemical transport model, dispersion models, and statistical models), data from different instruments on-board of satellites (GOME-2 and TROPOMI), and ground based air quality observations.

The assimilation of MetOp satellite retrieved data in the Bulgarian Chemical Weather Forecast System and the downscaling of the model output with the Local Air Quality Management System for the city of Plovdiv led to improvement of simulated concentrations of surface pollutants.

The technology created for Plovdiv could be implemented for other Bulgarian cities, making possible more Municipalities in Bulgaria to benefit from the use of satellite air pollution information in the assessment and forecast of key pollutants concentrations. The algorithms can be adapted also to data from other instruments (e.g. TROPOMI-S5p) that have finer spatial resolution and could be used for data assimilation in the smaller domains of BgCWFS (Sofia region, Sofia city).

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